

MODERN INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES THE INFORMATION SOCIETY IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Abstract. *In the article are shown meaning and tasks of the process of globalization, informatizations of society and education, the role of modern ICT in the education system, the direction of the effective using of ICT, personal development and requirements for specialists in informatization society.*

Key words: *information, communication, digital technology, education, information society, information education.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, the 21st century is described as the age of high technologies, the age of thinking, the age of general information, the age of globalization. The term "Globalization" was first mentioned by the American scientist T. Levitt in 1983 in an article published in the "Harvard Business Review" magazine. This is what the author called the process of unification of various product markets produced by large multinational corporations. But in the present era, globalization is gaining a different meaning and importance. Globalization is a global process that has arisen as a result of human consciousness and thinking, it is a process of transition to an information society that does not know borders and territories, does not recognize systems, is continuously growing and developing. Thinking is a window showing the level of development of society. Both successes and failures are clearly visible in this window. It's no secret that a person's dignity and perfection is determined by the level of thinking. Information is the main factor influencing the extent to which human thinking and thinking ability are formed. Therefore, the development of the modern civilized society in the present period is characterized by the process of informatization.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Pedagogical observation, comparative analysis, generalization, pedagogical experiment-test, mathematical-statistical analysis, mental cards, expert survey of foresight, development of scenarios, future box, and Delphi methods were used in the research process.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Informatization of society is a global social process and a leading type of activity in the field of public production, a complex of processes of information collection, processing, storage, transmission and use with the help of modern microprocessor and computer techniques and other various technical means used in information exchange.

The emergence and development of the information society creates opportunities for the following in human life activities:

- the possibility of broad and active use of the intellectual potential accumulated in printed form during the systematic and constantly expanding and developing scientific, production and other activities of mankind;

- by integrating science, education, production on the basis of information and communication technologies, intensive development of all spheres of production of society, directing human labor from physical labor to mental labor, intellectualizing all types of human activity;

- to raise the information service to a higher level, to create an opportunity for any member of the society to access and use the source of reliable information, to visualize the provided information, to ensure the validity and viability of the information used.

Currently, the open information system, which is designed to use the information space possible for some areas of society, leads to the improvement of society's management mechanisms, its humanization and democratization, and the improvement of the standard of living of society members. The processes related to the informatization of society allow not only the development of scientific and technical progress, but also the intellectualization of all types of human activity, and the creation of a completely new information environment in terms of quality. It ensures the development of a person's creative potential. Informatization of education is one of the leading directions of the process of informationalization of society.

Informatization of education is a process aimed at the implementation of the spiritual and pedagogical goals of the educational process on the basis of methodologically and practically providing the educational field with modern information and communication technologies and technical means and using them effectively, which includes:

- improvement of the educational system management mechanism based on the use of scientific-pedagogical information, information-methodical materials and the automated data bank of communication networks;

- improvement of educational system methodology, organizational forms and strategy of educational content in accordance with the development goals of the learner in the conditions of modern information society;

- to create a methodical system aimed at developing the intellectual potential of the learner based on the independent acquisition of knowledge and the implementation of information-educational, research-research work, the formation of independent information processing abilities in various fields of his activity;

- creation and use of a computer-testing system of monitoring and evaluating the student's knowledge.

The following software devices and devices operating on the basis of microprocessors, computing techniques and other modern technical means of information exchange can be included in the modern information and communication technical means:

- digital technical means, including computers and personal computers;
- a complex of terminal devices designed for all classes of digital technical means, local computing networks, data input and transmission devices, text and graphic data input and manipulation tools, large-volume data storage tools and other peripheral devices of modern EHM;

- means of transferring data from graphic or sound form to numerical data (or vice versa), audiovisual data manipulation tools and devices based on multimedia and "Virtual reality" technology;

- artificial intelligence systems;
- modern means of communication;
- machine graphics system, software packages (programming languages, translators, compilers, operating systems, application packages, etc.)

The widespread use of flexible automated systems, microprocessors, software control devices and robots in production has ensured the development of scientific and technical progress in the current period. This process sets before modern pedagogy the important task of preparing personnel who are fast-acting and quickly adaptable to the demands of the times at a qualitatively new stage of development based on the information of the society. This task, in turn, is considered a social order of the society and mainly depends on the provision of educational institutions with modern information and communication technical means and the level of readiness of learners to quickly receive and process the constantly growing flow of information. Therefore, one of the important tasks is to organize the effective use of modern ICT technical tools in order to increase the efficiency and quality of the educational process and intensification.

The relevance of the above tasks is determined not only by the social order of society, but also by the personal needs of the learner, which is related to the formation of self-development, improvement and assessment skills in a person-oriented education system.

The effective use of modern information and communication technical tools in the educational process provides ample opportunities for:

- establishment of rapid feedback between modern information and communication technical means and their users;
- computer visualization, virtualization of educational information about a certain object, technological processes or process laws;
- storage of large amounts of information in the archive and its transfer, easy access to the central data bank of the user and the possibility of working on the data;
- automation of the information search and calculation process, multiple and multi-factor processing of the results of training and experience, the possibility of repeating it;
- automation of informational and methodological support of the educational process, organization of management and control and evaluation of learning results.

These opportunities show that the use of modern information and communication technologies in the educational process is more effective in the following directions:

- recording, collecting, storing, processing information about the studied object, event, situation, as well as transferring large amounts of information in various forms;
- interactive dialogue, that is, communication, interaction between the software system and its user;
- management of real objects (for example, educational robots, simulated industrial devices and mechanisms, etc.);
- managing various objects, events, processes, including actual processes by displaying them on the screen;
- automated control over the results of educational activities, processing of control results, monitoring, training, testing, etc.

CONCLUSION

The types of activities listed above are based on the informed interaction between the student, the teacher and new information technologies, and they serve to realize educational goals. Therefore, it will not be a mistake to call the directions related to these types of activities information-educational goals.

In the conditions of the information society, the development of the learner's personality based on ICT requires special attention to the following tasks:

- development of thinking and thinking abilities of the learner;
- development of cultural education based on computer graphics, multimedia technologies;
- formation of the ability to make optimal decisions in complex non-standard situations or to make specific proposals for problem solving (for example, by using computer games aimed at optimizing activities, etc.);
- development of the student's research activity using the possibilities of computer modeling;
- forming the learner's information culture, the ability to use and process information correctly.

Timely resolution of the above-mentioned issues related to the informatization of society, in other words, the fulfillment of the social order of society, the training of qualified personnel in the field of information-communication and computer engineering, and the correct and effective use of all users of modern information technology technical means (including the population). shows that skill development is one of the most urgent and important tasks of today.

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